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Why the separation of theology and biblical studies is scientifically appropriate and important

Abstract

Theology means, if one analyzes the origin of the word, as 'dealing with the ideas/intentions of God'. As a teaching subject in the modern sense, theology has developed only in the course of the encounter of clergy and Greek philosophy. In fact, theology has been understood as a reflection of religious practice from the beginning, a practice very common in Judaism and later also in Christianity. But why do we as humanity need theology? We will see that without theology a deep layer of humanity would remain unreflected, a layer far deeper than the "psyche". However, we will also see that a scientific study of the Bible is of high importance. Theology and biblical studies are two important but separate entities.

Discussion

What is the relationship between religious practice (whatever that may be in detail) and theology as a reflection of that practice? Are there normative approaches in any respect that might even distinguish "right" from "wrong" practice? And if there are: Where is the norm to be found or how to justify it? A basic question is to what extent people can talk at all about God, who for theistic believers is not an integral part of the representational human world. Pantheists and panentheists have a much easier time at this point. Now, theists have to question whether humans can actually establish and form more than a formal relationship with God. Theistic theology has as a constitutive reference point, the Messiah, who of course from a panentheistic point of view is only

one aspect of the One and Threefold - albeit an extremely important aspect. If theists speak of God, do they really speak of Him or only of their respective subjectively coined image of God, which actually must not exist at all, if one follows the Holy Scriptures. Panentheists, for whom there is no separation of creator and creation anyway, find much easier access to God in this respect, especially about being interwoven with the Holy Spirit. Different, here only coarsely describable relationship determinations have developed in this respect in the course of the long history of theology. In the Middle Ages, the model developed by Thomas (Aquin) on the basis of Aristotelian philosophy was fundamental, which assumes a twofold division of human cognitive abilities: Man is by himself able to recognize the existence of a deity or a divine being or, at any rate, of an original principle of all being; this ability, however, which exists in the nature of man on the basis of divine creative action, is not sufficient to perceive God as a concretely acting person in history.

Who God really is, God himself must manifest - and this he has done according to theistic conception with the Torah and the Bible. For panentheists, this clinging to a compendium inspired by the Holy Spirit but compiled by humans can never be the sole foundation of faith. For them the very intimate and immediate relation to God is essential, to His pantheistic aspect (Holy Spirit), as well as to His panentheistic aspect (thanks to the incarnation of the transcendent aspect of God into the human body we all know as Jesus of Nazareth), possible without auxiliary constructs. Thus, theology cannot simply be the reflection of the divine revelatory insights grounded in the Bible and handed down in the communities of faith. Compared to the individual experience of the omnipresent and future-moving vitality of the Holy Spirit, theology must inevitably take a back seat.

However, it must also be stated that mankind witnesses the self-revelation of the transcendent portion of God only on the idea (logos) of the Gospels. However, the Bible itself is not central, but what it knows to report is. Therefore, one should not fall into the trap of attaching the Judeo-Christian faith to scriptures, but to the core messages about which these scriptures report. The personal relationship with the Holy Spirit leads to rightly guided knowledge; statements of faith cannot be scientifically verified or falsified. This is and remains the task of biblical studies, but not of theology.

Within the last centuries, theology has also been divided into sub-disciplines, which has led to a loss of a holistic view. The work on the "original document", i.e. the Holy Scriptures, with focus on the direct experience of God in thought, action and experience thus remains central - or should become central again. Biblical studies, on the other hand, focus on the historical research of the origin, the redaction and the already internally recognizable impact history of the individual writings. It does not have the task to bring a gain of knowledge in view of the situation of origin, but it serves to prevent a rash appropriation of biblical texts, which are often taken out of context

especially by lay preachers or underqualified clergymen. In this way, however, biblical studies ensure that the Holy Scriptures with their manifold statements is just as indispensable as theology as a source of the message to mankind. The Bible challenges us to enter into conversation with it, to question it and to be questioned by it, to what extent the story of God that can be read there can be interwoven with our own life story. Therefore, a purely spiritual or a purely scientific approach would be insufficient in each case. Lay preachers, but also some intellectually weak clergymen, who deal with the Bible as if it had fallen from the heavens as the word of God, are a cause for concern. The humiliation of Judaism and Christianity as "book religions" is a Muslim narrative that Jews and Christians must, under no circumstances, adopt as their own. There is not even a consensus whether the Judeo-Christian God and the Islamic "Allah" are equivalent. The authors of this text doubt that Allah is identical with the Judeo-Christian God.

Whoever as a Judeo-Christian believer, clergyman or scholar follows this satanic Islamic narrative betrays the core of the Judeo-Christian faith and is unfit for any office in both religions, Judaism and Christianity. In scientific discourse with Muslim clergy, one can and should uncompromisingly put a stop to this appropriation and foreign interpretation of one's own faith and inform the respective Muslim that an interreligious dialogue on the basis of the Muslim understanding of the Bible is unacceptable and spiritually totally impossible.

The correct classification of the role of the Bible can help, which is done by historicizing and contextualizing (biblical studies) as well as by explaining biblical texts to people without previous theological knowledge. Thereby the richness of biblical horizons is infinite. Systematic biblical studies, which researches faith scientifically, also serves to present and discuss faith in its spiritual dimension without controversy. It cannot be a matter of educating uncritical minds, but it has the task of making possible this elementary confrontation of one's own person with the contents of faith. The goal should always be to critically reflect one's own convictions and not to apologetically defend all statements of one's faith community. The goal should always be to attain one's own biblical competence before projecting one's faith onto third parties.

Conclusion

The task of biblical studies is to understand the faith scientifically. It does not have the task of substantiating it. To regard the Bible as a source of theological knowledge does not yet imply normative practice. However, it is not biblical studies that are normative, but a theological and, above all, the personal relationship of every human being to the Holy Spirit and, of course, to the transcendent part of God Himself who incarnated in a man called Jesus of Nazareth to become the Messiah.

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